

Restructuring Public Autonomous Bodies of Housing Urban Development Punjab to Succeed In a Highly Competitive Environment

Author Details: Mr. Abubakar Nazir Khan

Bahria University, School of Management Sciences, 47 C Civic Centre, Johar Town Lahore, Pakistan

Abstract

the objective of carrying out the research is to transform the autonomous bodies into well performing bodies lacking the quality of services in their mandated area which is quite deficient primarily due to their institutional design, including issues of autonomy, governance and professional capacity at all levels. This has led to a continuous decline of various service delivery indicators which despite heavy capital investments and annual subsidies have not translated into improved services. The research will be based on doing the critical review of the Legal documents, policies and practices of organization. GAP analysis will be conducted by obtaining reliable data on legal matters, Human resource, Regulatory, financing and Technical efficiency to conduct comparison of actual vs. potential performance and best use of current resources. Reforms or restructure plan will be prepared on the basis of GAP analysis and Critical review and will suggest KPI's.

Keywords: KPI's, Autonomous bodies, Professional Capacity, Legal Matters, Human resource, Regulatory, financing and Technical efficiency

1. INTRODUCTION

The term autonomous bodies refer to the bodies which has sole right to establish their own laws and code of conduct. Its own top managerial staff can determine the standards of administration for the body (Singh, 2017). For simplicity sake, normally the boards of such bodies receive the guidelines of the concerned Government or division under which they work, but only passing the resolutions to that effect. Housing Urban Development and Public Health Engineering Department (HUD&PHED), Government of Punjab, responsible to devise and implement scalable, equitable and sustainable water, sewerage and drainage programs and projects across the province except five big cities namely:

- WASA Lahore.
- WASA Faisalabad.
- WASA Rawalpindi.
- WASA Multan.
- WASA Gujranwala

Figure 1 Organogram of HUD&PHED

1.1 PROBLEM STATEMENT

The need to do restructuring of a public organization is that in public organization especially the organizations which are autonomous body (because they denote an independent body subject to its own laws) are facing a lot of challenges/problems in planning, execution operations and Monitoring & control.

Problems hampering smooth operation of such bodies in Punjab are rather well documented. These problems can be grouped as legal/policy-related, institutional and technical. Issues such as legal anomalies related to dual institutional controls; hazy linkages with respective local government institutions and provincial line departments; inability to provide continuous services of acceptable quality; weaknesses in undertaking requisite maintenance operations; near complete dependence on government for investments; hesitation to employ sound business models for full cost recovery; very weak HR regime covering personnel as well as systems; undue political influences especially in the working of staff and labor unions; near absence of sound performance monitoring systems; missing adherence to mutually accepted Key Performance Indicators are some of the more well-known constraints hampering desirable performance from such bodies in Punjab.

It should therefore not come as a surprise that nearly all bodies in Punjab are loss making entities with development and operational shortfalls over last years. It is this overarching context that has led me sense of doing my research within my parent department (HUD&PHED) as fully functional service delivery entities performing in line with benchmarks and standards governing functioning of similar organizations at the global level.

1.2 OBJECTIVES

To suggest autonomous bodies an independent professional entity with clearly defined areas of responsibility, coupled with commensurate financial & administrative authority and a single line of objective & performance based accountability.

1.3 SIGNIFICANCE

This study can provide project managers and different professionals working in administrative departments to make their organization a profitable and free from anomalies. The key reform is to make autonomous bodies an independent professional entity with clearly defined areas of responsibility, coupled with commensurate financial & administrative authority and a single line of objective & performance based accountability. This study will be helpful for the organization/body which is providing an institutional autonomy and control system, will create roles that are feasible for the employee, will change nature of business, will introduce new management methods with quality, help to reduce finance issues, will provide organization legal compliance, will help organization eliminate gaps in technical capacities of core staff and eliminate anomalies in system of recruitment, mobility and career progression.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Based on research objective following question is formed:

Are the autonomous bodies not well oriented about best practices and skills required for effective and efficient service delivery?

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

“Restructuring is characterized as an alteration in the operational structure, financing structure and administration structure of an association” (Gibbis, 2007).

“Restructuring of diverse activities, for example, divestiture of failing to meet business expectations, turnoffs, acquisitions, stock repurchases and debts swaps, which are onetime trade, yet furthermore fundamental changes introduced in day to day business” (Sterman, 2002).

Research by Loomis and Rdriguez (2009) states organizational restructuring is changing the old ways of working in an organization to the new ones.

It is perceived that “the idea of restructuring is worried about changing methods of working from short term benefits to long term benefits. The idea of restructuring dates to the 1960’s and advanced to organizational development” (Cooper rider & Sekerka, 2006). Theories of organization change were utilized to frame the calculated road map for the restructuring (Boomer & Rueben, 2005). Restructuring in an organization can be difficult in light of the fact better methods of working together/administration and it assumes changes in regular working methods/SOP’s (Hind & Baruch, 2000). At the point when associations experience real changes, the executives assume a vital job, as the administration is essentially has the key responsibility of making the staff motivated to accomplish the ideal results. It is similarly stand out among the difficult responsibilities that administration face.

At some points Curri (2002) likewise underlined the requirement for the administrative interventions in change. It is additionally articulated that organized productivity might be accomplished after a reorganizing, if the associations among the executives and (specialized and non-specialized) staff happened dependent on the Road map it will affect the organization in a positive way.

As indicated by Kezar and Eckel (2002), the executives might be significantly more fruitful with the change procedure, if institutional culture was a piece of the underlying initial restructuring discussion. Despite the fact that changes are generally arranged by the board the people in charge of executing the progressions are the employees.

Directors and managers should emphasize the significance of making a domain that elevates employee spirit to achieve effective organizational change (LÜScher & Lewis, 2008). According to (Boomer & Rueben, 2005), workers would almost certain participate in changes in the event that they trusted that the supervisors were reliable and proficient about the circumstance. Hierarchical change, particularly which includes restructuring, regularly incorporates changes in the reporting structure. Throughout the years, institutions have naturally changed the manner in which people connect with one another in connection to the structures made (Fleming, 2011). The reason for change inside Public associations can start from either interior or outer conditions.

Organization rebuilding procedures comprises of three modes; portfolio, Financial related and hierarchical rebuilding. Hierarchical rebuilding includes the adjustments in HR strategies. The present HR strategies of the association may should be changed as per the evolving situation. The organization office needs to empower change the executives (Bowman & Singh, 1999)

As mentioned by the Srivastava and Mushtaq (2011) on the effect of rebuilding on the operational viewpoints. They utilized changes in financing. Their investigation found that there were critical enhancements in all out income, overall revenue, and profit for resources following restructurings.

Another examination directed via Airo (2009) investigates upgrades in the corporate execution of firms associated with acquisition. Utilizing an example of organizations in the period from 1996 to 2005 in the administrations divisions, their outcomes demonstrate that achievement in the service sector has contributed in improving the profitability of firms.

In Punjab, Pakistan there are 140 different autonomous bodies that are working in line with the public bodies facing different institutional challenges like legal matters, financing, human resource, accountability, regulatory and Technical efficiency. In many cases the employees of these organizations seen absence of expert aptitudes is serious barrier for basic leadership in the organization. This together with elevated level of technocracy propose that specialist culture is developed in the organization. While self-administration depends on generalist culture – "individuals with various abilities who can perform each other's occupations and substitute as necessities emerge" (Nils Brede Moe & Dyba, 2009).

According to report of Jensen (2017) in numerous regards, restructuring public organizations is a more troublesome assignment than controlling private elements: a few authorizations, for example, Fines and punishments, can't be utilized, or they can be passed on to citizens, weakening the effectiveness motivating forces. Also, bureaucratic hierarchies of importance may oblige administrative adequacy if the regulator does not have the authority to impose its decisions on regulated entities further up the hierarchy.

On the positive side, the monetary direction of public organizations can be structured utilizing bench-marking, daylight control and utility-specific execution pointers to drive productivity. whereas it also highlights the need for the autonomous

bodies to be sufficiently autonomous and to have the capacity to meet the regulatory reporting requirements before it can give desired services.

2.1 Organizational KPI's

The Key Performance Indicators is used by the organization in order to ensure that the organization is moving in right direction and ensuring the targets in terms of organizational goals and objectives. The organizational KPI's are used to evaluate and control the overall business operations (Ghalayini, 1996). Thus the performance of organization measurements starts from the indication of performance process in an organization.

2.2 Organizational Financing

Organizational Financing is planning, organizing and directing the financial assets of the firm. The challenge in finance department of any organization is directly related to the knowledge of the procurement allocation and management of funds for the revenue generation of the organization (Priya & Mercy, 2016). The success behind any financially strong organization depends upon the efficient management of finances. In this research organization is evaluated on the current financial management techniques and how well they are contributing towards the sustainable financial management.

2.3 Organizational Human Resources

The effect of human asset the executives on the performance of an organization is one of the vital factor. It has turned into an area that requires giving careful consideration. As indicated by few investigations, some human asset practices will positively affect an associations execution while various scientists propose that increasingly reasonable and practical methodology is critical on these works (Delery & Jason D. Shaw, 2001). In spite of the fact that, representatives in an association are viewed as the most essential resource controlled by an association in any case, their effect are felt by just a couple of organizations (Schein, 2006)

2.4 Organizational Technical Efficiency

Organization technical efficiency is characterized as the capacity of the working units assessed to utilize ideal asset levels for their output. Technical efficiency portrays the capacity of working units to change inputs, to the output, it deals with its creation outskirts (Farrell, 1957). Utilizing this definition, a public organization is viewed as effective in the event that it delivers the most extreme measure of output from a given input (output-oriented efficiency) or on the other hand, in the event that it creates a given output with a minimum utilization of assets (input-oriented efficiency). Most associations utilize an input-oriented model since it is expected that public organizations can't dismiss their public demands, while they can lessen asset assignment and utilization levels. On the other hand, if public organization are required to enhance the suitability of systems, while keeping up the measure of assets, output-oriented model can rather be proposed.

2.5 Organizational Regulations

Regulations compliance in any organization is defined how well they are in lined with the existing laws and policies of the state. Regulatory organization can be structured in different ways, and choices about their organizational structure can impact regulators' behavior and performance, both overall as well as at the level of individual employees (Carrigan & Poole, 2015). regulatory organizations can be structured in a variety of ways and focus particular attention on the implications of those choices in organizational structure.

2.6 Organization Legal Matters

In every developing organization, the law provides the standard laws and policies for the smooth functioning of the organization with the state entities. These entities include, among others, the business corporation, the cooperative corporation, the nonprofit corporation, or the public organizations (Hansmann & Kraakman, 2001) . Public organizational law governs the relationship between individuals and the government and those relationships between the government which are of direct concern with the society.as of organization the law comprises of constitutional law and the administrative law. The organization law of the public bodies ensures that they can make decisions about the rights of individual and about their employees. Organizational law regulates bureaucratic managerial procedures with the autonomy of the organization and defines the powers, roles and responsibilities of the administrative agencies.

The above Literature review helped us to decide and developed the accompanying Hypothesis.

3 HYOTHESIS RESEARCH MODEL

3.1 HYPOTHESES

H1: Organizational KPI's have significant effect on organization performance.

H2: Organizational Financing have significant effect on organization performance.

H3: Organizational Human resource policies and practices have a significant influence on performance of organization.

H4: Organizational technical efficiency of their equipment and assets and have significant effect on organization performance.

H5: Organization has satisfactory regulatory system that have significant effect on organization performance.

H6: Organization legal matters are free from anomalies and have legal framework which has significant effect on performance of organization.

In continuation with the above mentioned hypotheses, following research model has been proposed.

3.2 RESEARCH MODEL

4 METHODOLOGY

The paper will be divided in four work streams, broadly mapping the four tasks. Task 1 will entail detailed analysis of existing policy and operational documents covering working of WASAs in particular the mechanics of urban water sector in general in the province. Task 1 will enable me to arrive at findings of critical review of the sector alongside a gap analysis which will cover institutional and technical aspects of the working of WASAs in the province. Under Task 2, findings of gap analysis will be used for the preparation of reform options and WASA restructuring plan including roles and responsibilities which will tackle all the operational level matters based on the “Critical Review and GAP Analysis Report”. Task 3 will be followed by development of detailed Manual for Utility Reform/Restructuring. Task 4 will be set of KPIs related to all aspect as a result of proposed Reform/Restructure Plan which will be used as benchmark.

Quantitative research will be carried out There are several methods used widely for data collection namely observations and Questioners. In order to collect primary data questioners will be structured on the basis of existing KPI's and Goals/objectives of Research. To collect data officials of these departments will be engaged in the survey. Questioners will be spread out in respective organizations and will be examined/measured statistically. Secondary research refers to the collection, study, evaluation and examination of second hand data, data that is already collected and is available. This research is based on a mixture of secondary and primary research. The sources of secondary research are legal and administration laws, past organization artefacts that can be useful and beneficial in the research.

4.1 POPULATION OF THE STUDY

Population is the total collection of elements from which inferences are made. Population refers to an entire group of persons or elements that have at least one thing in common. It also refers to all possible cases which are of interest for the study (Sekaran & R. G. Bougie, 2009). Total no of population is 450.

4.2 DATA COLLECTION

The study collected both primary and secondary data and utilized quantitative data (Cooper & Schindler, 2007) explain that Quantitative data is one in the form of numerals. This study used close-ended questions with a 5-point Likert scale to measure the objectives. It is designed to examine how strongly subjects agree or disagree with a statement (Sekaran & R. G. Bougie, 2009). 5-point Likert scales are used because they are more reliable and can provide more information. (Waiganjo & Elegwa Mukulu, 2013) used the likert scale on his study about effect of competitive strategies on the relationship between strategic human resources management and firm's performance. Questionnaires were administered to the selected team of employees, choice for the questionnaire was informed by its abilities to give respondents freedom to express their views or opinions more objectively. The technique used for sampling is convenience sampling and the it is distributed to 450 respondents out which 304 people submitted their response which is 67.5%.

4.3 Data Analysis

Once data collection is done the next significant step was to analyze the data and draw conclusions considering the main aim of the study as mentioned earlier, the data was collected through questionnaires and then afterwards it was put in SPSS software by defining the questions with different codes.

5 Critical Reviews

The present section is designed to provide a critical review and gap analysis covering WASAs and urban water sector in the Punjab. The review and gap analysis will lead to development of roadmap for utility reform and restructuring plan for five WASAs in the Punjab. The paper will provide an overall contextual background for urban water sector in the Punjab which will be followed by a brief introduction to five WASAs in the Punjab.

As per the Bureau of Statistics Punjab (2014), about 94% of the people used improved source of drinking water– 89% in urban areas and 97% in rural. Further, 19.2% population of the Punjab province has access to tap water followed by 41.7% motorized pump and 30.6% hand pumps. The amount of population using tap water is greater in the urban developed areas, 39.2% as associated to only 9.6% in rural areas. As per (Government of Pakistan Ministry of Science and Technology, 2015), nearly 35% water sources in the Punjab are harmless for consuming as a drinking water- free from micro-biological and chemical pollution (iron, fluoride and nitrates) and physical characteristics (turbidity, hardness, and total dissolved solids “TDS”) compared to 31% in the rest of the country.

5.1 WASAs in the Punjab - Legal Landscape:

Following section is designed to provide an overview of legal and policy landscape governing the working of WASAs in the Punjab.

5.1.1 Punjab Environmental Protection Act 1997:

PUNJAB ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION ACT (1997) has certain provisions for water and sanitation sector. Water is one of three major important components of environment. It is one of the primary concerns in the definitions of pollution, industrial activity and project. National Environmental Quality Standards (NEQS) set for the safe disposal of domestic, commercial and industrial solid and liquid waste and Water Standards for various purposes are to be followed under the PEPA. The Provincial Environmental Protection Agency is empowered to establish standards for quality of water under section 6(1)(g) of (THE PUNJAB ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION ACT , 1997) . Any violation of these standards carry penalties under section 11 (pollution charge) and section 17 (fine up to five million rupees) of (THE PUNJAB ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION ACT , 1997). Any proposed change of water use is a project which may require filing and approval of initial environmental examination or environmental impact assessment before initiation of work on the project. The enactment is not up to the mark as Environmental Protection Department (EPD) and Provincial Environmental Protection Agency lack capacity and well-defined interdepartmental coordination mechanism to enforce the Act and environmental quality standards.

5.1.2 Lahore Development Authority Act 1975 and the Punjab Development Cities Act (PDCA) 1976:

- Water and Sanitation Agencies (WASAs) in the Punjab have been created (THE LAHORE DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY ACT, 1975) and (THE PUNJAB DEVELOPMENT OF CITIES ACT, 1976) (PDCA) to carry on the elements of the Authority in connection to advancement, activity and upkeep of water supply, sewerage and drainage framework inside the limits of individual Development Authority (Section 2(a) The Punjab Development of Cities Act, 1976 (Pb Act XIX of 1976) (“PCDA”))
- The WASAs are being organized and managed by a mix of elected government representatives and the provincial government. However, after amendments in the LDAA 1975 in 2013 and PDCA 1976 in 2014, the role of local governments has been curtailed except that Mayor is one of the Members of the Authority.
- The accountability of the Authority and its agencies has not been well defined and elaborated in the PDCA besides that Authority is to perform duties and be channeled by any direction as the Government may give from time to time (Section 16). Further the element of monitoring by the Authority and even the Government, with any guidelines or parameters, to monitor the agencies have not been expressed.
- The Authority shall prepare an annual budget statement for the next financial year showing the estimated receipts and expenditure of the Authority and its agencies and shall submit the same to the Provincial Government for approval (Section 30). The accounts of the Authority and each of its agencies shall be audited annually (Section 31).
- Further the agency is tied under the Provincial Government and does not enjoy monetary or working independence.

5.1.3 Key Performance Indicators for WASAs in the Punjab

Table 1 Key Performance Indicators for WASAs in the Punjab

Indicators	Current Status					
	Unit	WASA Multan 2015	WASA Faisalabad 2015	WASA Gujranwala 2016	WASA Rawalpindi 2015	WASA Lahore (2016)
Water Supply Complaints	%	6.53	0.86	0.71	1.5	0.45
Sewerage Complaints	%	11.24	1	3	2.1	3.15

Waste water Treatment – Primary	%	-	0	0	-	0
Waste water Treatment – Secondary	%	-	5.91	0	-	0
Average Revenue of Water & Waste water	Rs./m3	3.11	7.25	1.08	4.1	6.85
Collection Period	Months	-	57	1267.03	12	550.43
Billing Efficiency	%	90	99.91	86.45	100	91.3
Collection Efficiency (Physical)	%	30.42	27.23	14.67	65	64
Collection Efficiency (Financial)	%	57	69.131	8.12	76	81
Operational cost coverage	Ratio	0.26	0.56	0.07	0.2	0.43

* Integrated Development & Asset Management Plan for the years 2016-17, 2017-18 & 2018-19 for WASA Faisalabad, WASA Multan & WASA Rawalpindi

** Key Performance Indicators of WASA Gujranwala issued by PWON 2016

*** Key Performance Indicators of WASA Lahore 2016

**** Estimates from World Bank Presentation 2014/2015

6 Findings of WASA Gap Analysis

6.1 Legal framework

- A wide range of legal and procedural inconsistencies and contrasts exist in the status of WASAs in respect to (THE PUNJAB DEVELOPMENT OF CITIES ACT, 1976), and (THE PUNJAB LOCAL GOVERNMENT ACT , 2013)
- A legislative review has not been thoroughly undertaken for developing a cohesive legal framework for urban water supply and sanitation services.
- In addition to clarity about status, procedural clarity is also missing in terms of ownership of assets and structures created under WASAs.
- There are major legal anomalies whereby the development authorities are deemed largely responsible for development and regulation of new and existing housing schemes with little inclination towards operation and maintenance of water supply.
- Necessary legal provisions are missing for incorporation of WASAs as legal entities with requisite autonomy from government except with regard to ownership and adherence to government regulation.
- There are no legal or procedural provisions for setting up and adherence to drinking water quality standards, monitoring and enforcement procedures
- Lack of tariff review procedures and guidelines adversely hampers performance of WASAs and overall urban water sector in terms of institutional health and performance
- There are huge procedural voids in terms of allocation of responsibilities and availability of enabling system for boosting of professional capacities of WASAs?
- Lack of effective performance monitoring mechanisms and sanctions is leading to perverse performance outcomes
- There is no mandatory disclosure of water quality at source and at user end and its periodic review.

6.2 Regulatory framework

- No single regulatory and monitoring authority exists for M&E and reporting of drinking water, sanitation and hygiene in the province.
- Multiple institutions/ departments conduct need assessment and execution of WASH projects with poor coordination and knowledge management.
- Presently, service provider is simultaneously leading on developing policy and implementation frameworks and regulating the services.

- Service providers are not fully empowered to set service standards and rationalization of tariffs hence WASAs are looking towards the Provincial Government for subsidies to meet their operational expenditures.
- Currently, no satisfactory regulatory system exists to mitigate challenges pertaining to contamination of drinking water sources and safe disposal/ treatment of human excreta in all WASAs. There is hardly any emphasis on water quality.

6.3 Financing

- Drinking water is one of the highly politically contested issues especially in major urban areas of Pakistan when it comes to financing decisions. WASAs are empowered to lay any fee or charge services for water supply and sanitation under the PLGA 2013 and LDAA/ PDCA but an approval and consent is required from the Provincial Government. Further, as per PDCA, in case of shortfall of revenue of the authority, the Provincial Government should provide funds for efficient service delivery by the authority. Therefore, the tariff is regulated by the consent of the Provincial Government. This places WASAs in disadvantaged position to identify additional measures and tariff rationalization for income generation, as these are not under the control of WASAs.
- The tariffs for domestic consumers have not been revised since 2011 but the price of electricity and other consumables have been increased significantly in last five years evident from the fact that more than 2/5th of total operational cost is being spent on electricity bills.
- The PDCA states that the Authority should prepare annual budget for the next financial year showing the estimated receipts and expenditure of the Authority and its agencies and shall submit the same to the Provincial Government for approval. The accounts of the Authority and each of its agencies shall be audited annually. All WASAs prepare their annual budget and receive subsidies from the provincial government to meet its operational costs. As evident from KPIs, recovery of operational cost ratios are very low indicating serious reforms in budgeting and financing processes of WASAs.

6.4 Human Resource Development

- The staff working at WASAs is expected to work as competent professionals but being a public sector organization, these are not well oriented about best practices and skills required for effective and efficient service delivery.
- The Annual Confidential Appraisals are conducted for key staff but these are not linked with any professional development and career progression paths. In the absence of systematic need assessment for skill development, the staffs have rare opportunities for continuous professional development.
- The current ratio of staffing in WASAs is also not in line with regional standards and acceptable practices; there is a need for careful review current deployment and placement strategy of human resources.
- The current procedures for placement and continuous skill development of senior staff are inadequate and lagging when compared with regional best practices

6.5 Technical Efficiency

- One key challenge noted by all WASAs is proper maintenance and management of their equipment and assets. This is further compounded by the increasing demand from a growing population and lack of necessary funds for investment. This leads to high levels of leakage, although lack of metering prohibits firm estimates. Hence operational efficiency is poor due to old and worn-out equipment such as pumping plant and overhead reservoirs, and these are not integrated in the planning process due to non-availability of funds.

7 Results and Discussion

7.1 Data Reliability

The threshold value of Cronbach alpha is 0.70 as the highest or 0.60 as the lowest threshold limit. As the table above shows that our value is greater than 0.7 so our data is stated as reliable for the five independent variables.

Studying Variables	Cronbach Alpha
Technical Efficiency	0.716
Financing	0.792
Regulatory	0.735
Legal matters	0.723
Organizational KPI's	0.769
Human Resource	0.833

Table2 Cronbach Alpha

7.2 DEMOGRAPHICS

This section presents personal information of the respondents who participated in the research study.

7.2.1 Gender:

The results show majority of the respondents (91.78%) were male while (8.22%) of the respondents were female. This distribution depicts an unfair balance of gender in the public departments of the Punjab.

7.2.2 Age:

The study sought to establish the organization of the respondents, the results in table shows most of the respondents (37.2%) were aged between 31 and 39 years, 35.9% were aged between 40 and 49 years, 15.5% were aged below 30 years while 11.5% were aged 50 years & above. This means that the greatest number of employees in the WASA were of older generation.

7.2.3 Organization:

The study sought to establish the organization of the respondents, the results in table shows most of the respondents (27.6%) were from WASA Lahore, (21.6%) were from WASA Faisalabad, (18.4%) from WASA Rawalpindi, (16.8%) were from WASA Multan, (12.2%) were from WASA Gujranwala and (3.3%) from Secretariat HUD&PHED. This means that the greatest number of employees that responded were from WASA Lahore.

7.2.4 Job Cadre of the Respondents:

The study sought to establish the respondents' position in their respective organization in order to ascertain if they were equipped with relevant knowledge and experience on restructuring activities on the basis of the BPS Scale. The results of the study as shown on table indicated that majority (51%) of the respondents were lower level (BPS <16), (36.8%) were in the middle level (BPS 17&18) and a few (9.2%) were senior (BPS 19 and greater). This is due to the practice that the top management comprises of very few individuals as compared to those in the lower management level who are the majority in organizations. This profile distribution was important since the study aimed at capturing the opinions of all cadres of employees in the organization as a unit of observation.

7.2.5 Education Level of the Respondents:

It was important to establish the education level held by the respondents in order to ascertain if they were equipped with relevant knowledge and skills on restructuring. Table shows the level of education of respondents was sought and majority (47.7%) had Graduation, 25% had Diploma, 23.0% had post graduate education level, 3.3% had secondary education level.

7.3 Correlation Analysis

Pearson correlation coefficient was used to gauge the relationship between independent variables Regulatory, legal matters, Organizational KPI's, Human Resource, Financing and technical efficiency with the dependent variable well performing organization. The results indicated that the correlation between the variables is significant at the 0.01 level.

Table 3 Correlations between the Variables

		Correlations						
		TE	FE	R	L	OK	HR	DV
TE	Pearson Correlation	1						
FE	Pearson Correlation	.680**	1					
R	Pearson Correlation	.545**	.618**	1				
L	Pearson Correlation	.721**	.625**	.506**	1			
OK	Pearson Correlation	.625**	.703**	.542**	.604**	1		
HR	Pearson Correlation	.734**	.767**	.681**	.799**	.709**	1	
DV	Pearson Correlation	.703**	.403**	.507	.624**	.573**	.873**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

7.4 Hypotheses Testing Simple Linear Regression

Regression thus shows us how variation in one variable co-occurs with variation in another. It also helps in producing condition that portrays the insights connection between at least one independent variable and the dependednt variable. The regression analysis results were introduced utilizing, regression model summary tables, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) table and beta coefficients tables.

H1: Organizational KPI’s have significant effect on organization performance?

Table 4 Model Summary of Organizational KPI's

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.173 ^a	.030	.027	.72534

a. Predictors: (Constant), OK

Table 5 ANOVA of Organizational KPI's

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.874	1	4.874	9.265	.003 ^b
	Residual	158.886	302	.526		
	Total	163.760	303			

a. Dependent Variable: DV
b. Predictors: (Constant), OK

Table 6 Coefficients of Organizational KPI's

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.233	.199		16.239	.000
	OK	.158	.052	.173	3.044	.003

a. Dependent Variable: DV

Above (Table 4) represents the regression model on organizational KPI’s versus well performing organization. As presented in the table, the coefficient of determination R square is 0.03 and R is 0.173 at 0.05 significance level. The

coefficient of determination indicates that 3% of the variation on performance of organization is influenced by KPI's. This implies that there exists a positive significant relationship.

The Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results as shown in (Table 5) further confirms that the model fit is appropriate for this data since p -value of 0.003 which is less than 0.05. This implies that there is a significant positive relationship between organizational KPI's versus well performing organization.

The results further indicate that organizational KPI's have positive and significant effects on Performance of Organization (Table 6). The fitted model $Y = 3.233 + 0.158 * OK$. This implies that a unit change in KPI's activities will increase Performance by the rate of 0.173. Even when KPI's are nonexistence, performance is still positive at 3.233 indicating that there are other drivers of performance in the organization.

H2: Organizational Financing has a significant effect organization performance?

Table 7 Model Summary of Financing

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.203 ^a	.041	.038	.72105
a. Predictors: (Constant), FE				

Table 8 ANOVA of Financing

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.745	1	6.745	12.973	.000 ^b
	Residual	157.015	302	.520		
	Total	163.760	303			
a. Dependent Variable: DV						
b. Predictors: (Constant), FE						

Table 9 Coefficients of Financing

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.076	.212		14.499	.000
	FE	.200	.056	.203	3.602	.000
a. Dependent Variable: DV						

Above (Table 7) represents the regression model on organizational Financing versus well performing organization. As presented in the table, the coefficient of determination R square is 0.041 and R is 0.203 at 0.05 significance level. The coefficient of determination indicates that 4.1% of the variation on performance of organization is influenced by Financing.

The Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results as shown in (Table 8) further confirms that the model fit is appropriate for this data since p -value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. This implies that there is a significant positive relationship between organizational financing versus well performing organization.

The results further indicate that organizational financing have positive and significant effects on Performance of Organization (Table 9). The fitted model $Y = 3.076 + 0.2 * FE$. This implies that a unit change in financing activities will increase Performance by the rate of 0.203. Even when financing is nonexistence, performance is still positive at 3.076 indicating that there are other drivers of performance in the organization.

H3: Organizational Human resource policies and practices have a significant influence on performance of organization?

Table 10 Model Summary of Human Resources

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.373 ^a	.139	.136	.68329

a. Predictors: (Constant), HR

Table 11 ANOVA of Human Resources

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22.761	1	22.761	48.751	.000 ^b
	Residual	140.999	302	.467		
	Total	163.760	303			

a. Dependent Variable: DV
b. Predictors: (Constant), HR

Table 12 Coefficients of Human Resources

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.057	.256		8.022	.000
	HR	.463	.066	.373	6.982	.000

a. Dependent Variable: DV

Above (Table 10) represents the regression model on organizational Human Resources versus well performing organization. As presented in the table, the coefficient of determination R square is 0.139 and R is 0.373 at 0.05 significance level. The coefficient of determination indicates that 13.9% of the variation on performance of organization is influenced by Human Resources.

The Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results as shown in (Table 11) further confirms that the model fit is appropriate for this data since p -value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. This implies that there is a significant positive relationship between organizational Human Resources versus well performing organization.

The results further indicate that organizational Human Resources have positive and significant effects on Performance of Organization (Table12). The fitted model $Y = 2.057 + 0.463 \cdot HR$. This implies that a unit change in Human resources activities will increase Performance by the rate of 0.373. Even when Human Resources are nonexistence, performance is still positive at 2.057 indicating that there are other drivers of performance in the organization.

H4: Organizational technical efficiency of their equipment and assets and have significant effect on organization performance?

Table 13 Model Summary Technical Efficiency

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.163 ^a	.027	.023	.72651

a. Predictors: (Constant), TE

Table 14 ANOVA of Technical Efficiency

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.359	1	4.359	8.258	.004 ^b
	Residual	159.401	302	.528		
	Total	163.760	303			
a. Dependent Variable: DV						
b. Predictors: (Constant), TE						

Table 15 Coefficients of Technical Efficiency

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.303	.186		17.720	.000
	TE	.144	.050	.163	2.874	.004
a. Dependent Variable: DV						

Above (Table 13) represents the regression model on organizational Technical Efficiency versus well performing organization. As presented in the table, the coefficient of determination R square is 0.027 and R is 0.163 at 0.05 significance level. The coefficient of determination indicates that 2.7% of the variation on performance of organization is influenced by Technical Efficiency.

The Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results as shown in (Table 14) further confirms that the model fit is appropriate for this data since p -value of 0.004 which is less than 0.05. This implies that there is a significant positive relationship between organizational technical efficiency versus well performing organization.

The results further indicate that organizational Technical Efficiency have positive and significant effects on Performance of Organization (Table 15). The fitted model $Y = 3.303 + 0.144 * TE$. This implies that a unit change in Technical Efficiency activities will increase Performance by the rate of 0.163. Even when Technical Efficiency are nonexistence, performance is still positive at 3.303 indicating that there are other drivers of performance in the organization.

H5: Organization has satisfactory regulatory system that have significant influence on performance of organization?

Table 16 Model Summary of Regulatory

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.107 ^a	.011	.008	.73217
a. Predictors: (Constant), R				

Table 17 ANOVA of Regulatory

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.867	1	1.867	3.482	.063 ^b
	Residual	161.893	302	.536		
	Total	163.760	303			
a. Dependent Variable: DV						
b. Predictors: (Constant), R						

Table 18 Coefficients of Regulatory

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.399	.232		14.629	.000
	R	.109	.058	.107	1.866	.063

a. Dependent Variable: DV

Above (Table 16) represents the regression model on organizational Regulatory versus well performing organization. As presented in the table, the coefficient of determination R square is 0.011 and R is 0.107 at 0.05 significance level. The coefficient of determination indicates that 1.1% of the variation on performance of organization is influenced by Regulatory.

The Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results as shown in (Table 18) further confirms that the model fit is appropriate for this data since p -value of 0.063 which is greater than 0.05. This implies that there is a significant negative relationship between organizational regulatory versus well performing organization.

The results further indicate that organizational regulatory have negative effects on Performance of Organization (Table 21) and Null hypothesis are accepted.

H6: Organization legal matters are free from anomalies and have legal framework which has significant effect on performance of organization?

Table 19 Model Summary of Legal Matters

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.224 ^a	.050	.047	.71764

a. Predictors: (Constant), L

Table 20 ANOVA of Legal Matters

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.230	1	8.230	15.980	.000 ^b
	Residual	155.530	302	.515		
	Total	163.760	303			

a. Dependent Variable: DV
b. Predictors: (Constant), L

Table 21 Coefficients of Legal Matters

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.127	.180		17.410	.000
	L	.190	.048	.224	3.998	.000

a. Dependent Variable: DV

Above (Table 19) represents the regression model on organizational legal matters versus well performing organization. As presented in the table, the coefficient of determination R square is 0.050 and R is 0.224 at 0.05 significance level. The coefficient of determination indicates that 5.0% of the variation on performance of organization is influenced by legal matters.

The Analysis of variance (ANOVA) results as shown in (Table 20) further confirms that the model fit is appropriate for this data since p -value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. This implies that there is a significant positive relationship between organizational legal matters versus well performing organization.

The results further indicate that organizational legal matters have positive and significant effects on Performance of Organization (Table 21). The fitted model $Y = 3.127 + 0.190 * L$. This implies that a unit change in legal matters activities will increase Performance by the rate of 0.224. Even when Legal matters are nonexistence, performance is still positive at 3.127 indicating that there are other drivers of performance in the organization.

8 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

8.1 Conclusion

From the analysis the following conclusion was made. First the Human resource policies have a significant value in the organization. Water and sanitation agencies in the Punjab needs massive changes in the human resource policies to convert themselves in better performing organizations to compete in highly competitive environment. whereas from the analysis we found that the legal matters are also playing an important role in the organizational performance with the technical efficiency and financing. Organizational KPI's need to be changed for the better functioning of organization. whereas regulatory doesn't play a vital role in the performance of autonomous body.

This research is a part of the bigger picture which is to restructure the public autonomous bodies of the Punjab. And give them the autonomous power to perform in the wellbeing of the public. So that they can deliver the required services to the public in an efficient way with less input and greater output.

8.2 Recommendations:

On the basis of the analysis following SOPs/Manual for reforms and restructure plan is generated and is recommended to the autonomies bodies of Housing Urban Development Punjab.

8.3 SOPs / Manual for the utility reforms and restructure plan

The following Manual aims to support the effective implementation of services by water and sanitation agencies in Punjab, the recommendations and approaches to planning are in accordance with the acts of the country. This manual is intended to be used for the WASA staff, engineers, and supervisors as a resource for effective implementation of the procedures and policies.

The key objectives of this Part are to:

- To educate and inform respected WASA employees
- To encourage the effective and efficient delivery

Based on the quantitative research conducted main areas that WASAs need to focus, for successfully planning and providing water supply services to consumers. The criteria are categorized as:

- Organizational Principle
- Strategic Business Plan
- Key Performance Indicators
- Asset Management Plan
- Sustainable Financial Plan
- Human Resource Management

8.3.1 Organizational Principle

Water and sanitation agencies play a major role in a provincial service delivery to its citizens; subpar service and functionality can negatively impact the health and overall quality of the life of people. WASAs are responsible for planning, designing and construction of water supply, sewerage & drainage facilities for:

- New works
- Rehabilitation and augmentation of the existing systems
- Operation and maintenance of water supply, sewerage & drainage systems
- Billing and collection of rates, fees and charges for the services provided to consumers

An organizational principle represents the moral compass of an organization. The purpose of setting a principle is to both set a standard of professional behavior and indicates the obligations of an individual professional to his/her organization and team. The key proposed organizational principal values are as followed and in line with regulations:

- Putting the interest of the nation, the organization over oneself
- Not participating in illegal transactions of money or any transactions that are deemed as bribe for unethical service of water supply provision.
- Providing information and news to the public in a timely manner without any discrimination
- Providing excellent customer service and incorporating consumer/user complaints and feedbacks in policies
- Adhering to a well-planned, aiming for the achievement of the work keeping with the standards of quality, transparency and accountability

It is recommended that before appointment and allocation of the new staff members, a specific training on professional and organizational code of ethics should be organized for the newly hired staff members under the supervision of senior officials of WASAs.

8.3.2 STRATEGIC BUSINESS PLAN

The community and governments are demanding increased accountability, increased levels of service and efficiency from water utilities. A Strategic Business Plan addresses these issues and provides a framework within which the water utilities can provide these services in an efficient manner and can continue to improve its performance. The business plan should be developed through following steps:

Phase 1- Data Collection & Analysis

The overall objective is to collect, organize, and analyze data in order to understand the existing situation of utility and to lay the ground for the future projection. Understanding of the Utility's existing situation is one of critical success factor of a good business plan. The data collection and analysis should include:

- City Overview – Location, population and access/coverage of water and sanitation services.
- Policy & legislation- Key laws, Regulations and any approved policies or framework by the government related to drinking water and sanitation services.
- Management Structure – The current organogram and capacities to deliver the services including human and physical resources.
- Financial Data- Current revenue and expenditures
- Technical and Operational Data
- Stakeholders Management and Relationship
- SWOT Analysis – Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats

Phase II- Planning

- Clarify the purpose and vision of the service providers
- Develop the strategic objectives with clear targets that includes institutional, Technical/Operational, Social, Environmental and Financial Strategic Objectives
- Identify and suggest activities to achieve the desired objectives and targets
- Proposed the areas of improvements with performance measurement strategy
- Define indicators and methods of measuring the success
- Suggest the budget with resource gaps and means of revenue collection
- Propose implementation strategy

Phase III- Implementation

The implementation phase will include:

- Compliance to standards and Performance reporting against the agreed indicators
- Asset management and O&M Plans
- Financial Management and Human Resource Development
- Customers services

8.3.3 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

The table below outlines the KPI that should be used by Punjab WASA to monitor and evaluate water supply and sewerage performance for internal and external reporting.

Table 22 Proposed KPI's

Water Coverage	Pipe Breaks
Sewerage Coverage	Sewerage blockages
Water production	Pipe leakages
Water Consumption	Unit operational cost - water sold (production cost at consumer end)
Unaccounted for water	Unit operational cost - water produced (gross production cost)
Non-revenue water	Staff per 1000 water and sewerage connections
Prop. Of functional meters	Water supply staff per 1000 water connections
Metered water supply	Sewerage staff per 1000 sewerage connections
Salary cost as proportion of Operating costs	Waste water Treatment – Primary
Power /Electricity Costs as prop. of Operating Costs	Waste water Treatment – Secondary
Chemically Unfit Water Samples at Tap	Average Revenue of Water & Waste water
Biologically Unfit Water Samples at Tap	Collection Period
Water Quality - Samples having residual chlorine	Billing Efficiency
Water Supply Complaints	Collection Efficiency (Physical)
Sewerage Complaints	Collection Efficiency (Financial)

8.3.4 ASSET MANAGEMENT PLAN

All the assets of WASA, especially, pumping machinery and pumping station are very important components in water supply and sewerage system. The assets are subjected to wear, tear, erosion and corrosion due to their nature of functioning and use and therefore these are vulnerable for failures. To keep the assets up and available for use, assets should be properly operated and maintained. In the following sub sections, various activities/ schedules are detailed in respect of all the assets for effective operation and timely maintenance. The Asset Manager shall, in consultation with the Director O&M, prepare Asset Management Plan in respect of Water and Sanitation/ Sewerage Services

The Planning and Development Department from the Government of Punjab in conjunction with the Urban Unit has recommended and adopted the Integrated Development Asset Management Plan (IDAMP). All WASAs should follow the guidelines and processes suggested under IDAMP by Urban Unit. In the table below specific time-periods are suggested for WASA to develop and implement their asset management plans.

Table 23 WASA Planning Guidelines

Planning Horizon	WASAs Planning Instrument
Long Term	Master Plans (10-20 Years)
Medium Term	Integrated Development And Asset Management Plan (IDAMP) (Three Years)
Short Term	Annual Development Plan (ADP) (One Year)

8.3.5 FINANCIAL PLAN

A robust financial plan is a key element of a Water Utility's water supply or sewerage strategic business plan. The financial plan should clearly indicate how the business would finance the provision of services that meet levels of service negotiated with the community and the long-term commercial viability of the business.

- **Purpose and Objectives**

The overall purpose of Financial Planning is to achieve organizational sustainability with following specific objectives:

- Facilitate the record keeping of each accounting process;
- Ensure that books of account are prepared to conform to sound accounting policies;
- Enable the management to obtain accurate and timely financial reports on periodic basis
- Help organize and manage the assets and liabilities of the WASA's;
- Support coordination of accurate financial reporting and adequate financial disclosures;
- Promote compliance with an applicable reporting framework, law and regulations;
- Promote efficient financial management through the provision of useful reference materials and standard documents;

Process of Financial Planning

Step 1: Determine Your Current Financial Situation

Step 2: Develop Financial Goals

Step 3: Identify Alternative Courses of Action

Step 4: Evaluate Alternatives

Step 5: Create and Implement a Financial Action Plan

Step 6: Reevaluate and Revise Your Plan

8.3.6 HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT

Human Resource Management function has come to be recognized as an inherent part of any organization. It plays a vital role in the functionality and performance of water utilities. The function is charged with overall responsibility for implementing strategies and policies relating to the management of individuals (i.e. the Human Resource Management) thereby optimizing their contribution towards the realization of organizational objectives. Job descriptions and TOR for the main officials within the organization clearly lays out the responsibilities and expectations from each individual officer. It also helps to ensure that there is no overlapping of duties and responsibilities and prevents any conflict amongst the employees and overall organization.

Purpose and Objectives

The overall purpose of Human Resource Management is to improve the working efficiency of the organization with following specific objectives:

- To maintain awareness of and compliance with local, provincial and federal labor laws;
- To maintain employee record keeping and confidentiality;
- To make approved and accurate Salary and Wage adjustments;
- To develop accurate, complete and timely Payroll distribution;
- To Administer and record Employee Benefits as per organizational policy;
- To facilitates employee growth through regular capacity building programmes
- To manage the performance of each department and official in an efficient and effective way

Recruitment

Prior and during the recruitment process for a Terms of Reference (TOR) needs to be prepared for all vacancies and positions for permanent positions and consultants/ contact employees hired for projects. The Client and the Consultant's respective responsibilities should be clearly defined in the TOR. The typical information required in the TOR is summarized.

Staff Record:

Each water utility should maintain a clear record of all employees and contracted individuals outlining the role and responsibilities of their respected positions.

The HR policies, especially the recruitment process, need to be streamlined. A better option would be to use Management Information System to keep and track record regarding staff recruitment, transfer, relevant and demand-based placement etc. It is also extremely important to involve highly qualified and trained human resource in these agencies for services delivery. Capacity building of the existing staff in lines with their role and need assessment should be introduced. In this regard, annual performance and capacity evaluations of individual employees i.e. ACRs should be maintained as benchmarks for designing the departmental training programmes.

9 ROADMAP FOR WASA REFORM & RESTRUCTURING PLAN

Table 24 Restructure Plan

GOAL
<i>Achieving maximum access to optimum quantity of safe drinking water for residents of large cities of Punjab</i>
OUTCOME 1
Institutional capacity of Punjab WASAs in technically sound, profitable and environmentally sustainable manner
OUTCOME 2
State of the art and high quality Infrastructure & assets

Sr. No.	Reform Interventions	Reform Options	Roles and Responsibilities	Timeline	KPIs Year 1	KPIs Year2
Legal & Policy Reforms	1. WASA Incorporation as Authority	New Law enacted	PHED to initiate process for new legislation	2019-20 & 2020-2021	Draft Law developed after consultation	Law for WASA autonomy enacted
Institutional Reforms	1. Functional Autonomy & Clear Command lines	WASAs delinked from Member Provincial Assembly through administrative orders by Government	PHED moves summary for Chief Minister's Approval to achieve WASA autonomy	2019-20	Functional Autonomy for MD WASA demonstrated	
	2. Capacity building of managerial & technical HR	WASA Academy Law enacted as full scale	PHED to initiate process for new legislation	2019-20	In-Service Training of WASA technical staff begins	Pre-Service Training of WASA staff initiated
	3. Consumer Satisfaction	Rules for Client Orientation & Consumer Services	PHED develops Rules through consultative process and as per international best practices	2019-20	Client Orientation & Consumer Services Rules Notified	
	4. Tariff Rationalization	Develop a regulatory framework for tariffs	PHED, WASAs and Finance Departments	2019-20	Develop standards and framework	

Operational reforms	Key Performance Indicators	Performance Management Framework for WASA	WASAs with PHED	2019-20	Quarterly KPIs published and updated	
	Replacement of Outlived Infrastructure	Asset Management and Inventory System to be modernized for replacement of outlived infrastructure	PHED and WASAs to develop an incremental plan as part of WASA Master Plan	2019-20	Infrastructure Renovation & Asset Management Plan developed	replacement of outlived infrastructure and Assets
	Maintenance Operations	Robust O&M operations	PHED and WASAs	2019-20	TPV contractors hired	
Financial Reforms	Improved Revenue Collection	Own source revenue plan for enhancing financial assets	WASAs, PHED and Finance Department	2019-20	Revenue Enhancement Plan Developed	
	Curtailed Illegal Water Usage	Regularize the illegal water connection and reduce non-revenue water losses through appropriate legal provisions	WASAs	2019-20	Revise schedule of penalties, fee and fines	

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